

Action Potential recordings

HiPSC cardiac cells seeded on MCS-MEAs

HiPSC cardiac cells

Seeding on MEAs and Incubation

CO₂ SIMULTOX

Acute drug-induced effects

Administration of **Dofetilide 10 nM**

COO SIMULTOX

Acute drug-induced effects

Administration of **Dofetilide** at different concentrations

AP Comparison

APD Comparison

CO₂ SIMULTOX

Acute drug-induced effects

Administration of **Isoprenaline 1 μ M**

AP Comparison

APD Comparison

CO-SIMULTOX

Acute drug-induced effects

Administration of **Isoprenaline 2 μ M**

AP Comparison

APD Comparison

COO SIMULTOX

Long-term Analysis

COO **simultox**

